

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Banking sector development and Economic growth in South Asian Countries: Dynamic Panel Data Analysis

Sumaira¹, Robeena Bibi^{2*},

¹Department of Management Sciences, Islamia College University Peshawar, Pakistan

²School of Public Administration, Hohai University, Nanjing China.

Correspondence

Robeena Bibi

Corresponding Author:

khanrobeena321321@gmail.com

Received: -----

Revised: -----

Accepted: -----

Abstract

This study explores the contribution of banking sector development to economic growth for a sample of four south Asian countries namely, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Pakistan and India. The study employed Fixed Effect (FE), Difference GMM and System GMM models to the data set for the period of 1980 -2017. The findings of the study indicates that bank based financial development index constructed of private sector credit, board money(M2) and domestic credit provided by banks affect economic growth significantly and positively almost in all models. The result approves that bank based financial development contribute to economic growth and augment growth level in the sample countries. The findings conclude that bank based financial development is important in boosting economic growth and suggests sampled countries of this study government's channels and regulatory authority on further improvement on banking system in order to achieve higher economic growth.

Keywords: Banking sector development, economic growth; Difference GMM, System GMM, South Asian-4 countries

This is an open-access article published by the [Journal of Environmental Science and Economics](#), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited

1.Introduction

Financial development of a country plays very essential protagonist in a country economic growth. Financial intermediaries are important in investments monitoring and succor in increasing productivity level. (Schumpeter, 1911) have esteemed the role performed by financial intermediaries in economic development because these intermediaries choose firms where they use society's savings and perform their role in augmenting growth through the issuance of high quality of services related to financing. On the other side, (Lucas Jr, 1988) states the importance of financial development and its association with economic growth is overstrained. In the developmental economics review of (Demirgüç-Kunt & Levine,

2004), (Berman, Neumann, & Stern, 1989) haven't even discussed in the financial system omitted topics list. Levine (2004), and also another researcher (Grossman & Miller, 1988) have designated that financial market development and its impact on economic growth is a protruding intent to be studied. Similarly, (Gurley & Shaw, 1955), (Goldsmith, 1969), (Bagehot, 1873), (Fishkin, Keniston, & McKinnon, 1973) and Schumpeter (1911) have stated that finance growth nexus shouldn't be overemphasized without the substantially adopted economic growth (Cited by Levine, 2004). Some researcher's states assertion that finance influence economic growth only in developed countries and it's not true for low-income economies. Moreover, some other economists contend that financial development is only beneficial in the early stage of a country